

Supplemental Figures and Tables – Anandappa et al. 2023

Table S1. All species and accessions used in this study and the number of GC-MS replicates analyzed. Accessions source information either refers to USDA National Plant Germplasm System identifier (Plant Introduction number), commercial source information, or *H. annuus* accessions are listed as abbreviated versions of their name as listed in the methods.

Species	Accession Identifier/Source	Ploidy	Replicates
<i>Helianthus angustifolius</i>	PI 673210 (CRP)	Diploid	10
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	PI 673304 (KON)	Diploid	10
<i>Helianthus argophyllus</i>	PI 673306 (FLB)	Diploid	15
<i>Helianthus atrorubens</i>	PI 649940 (WAR)	Diploid	15
<i>Helianthus carnosus</i>	PI 673309 (FCR)	Diploid	5
<i>Helianthus debilis</i> subsp. <i>debilis</i>	UCF Arboretum	Diploid	4
<i>Helianthus debilis</i> subsp. <i>tardiflorus</i>	PI 673213 (CDK)	Diploid	16
<i>Helianthus decapetalus</i> 2N	PI 649972 (VA)	Diploid	8
<i>Helianthus decapetalus</i> 4N	PI 547169 (OH)	Tetraploid	7
<i>Helianthus divaricatus</i> 2N	PI 664645 (OH)	Diploid	5
<i>Helianthus divaricatus</i> 4N	PI 664604 (WI)	Tetraploid	3
<i>Helianthus floridanus</i>	Ames 32740 (OCK)	Diploid	4
<i>Helianthus giganteus</i>	PI 664647 (LCN)	Diploid	17
<i>Helianthus grosseserratus</i>	PI 613793 (ONA)	Diploid	9
<i>Helianthus heterophyllus</i>	PI 673162 (RAM)	Diploid	8
<i>Helianthus hirsutus</i>	PI 547204 (IL)	Tetraploid	3
<i>Helianthus laevigatus</i>	PI 664723 (NC)	Unknown	12
<i>Helianthus longifolius</i>	PI 650001 (FTP)	Diploid	3
<i>Helianthus maximiliani</i>	PI 613794 (LAW)	Diploid	2
<i>Helianthus microcephalus</i>	PI 673317 (MTR)	Diploid	2
<i>Helianthus mollis</i>	PI 673318 (PEM)	Diploid	8
<i>Helianthus occidentalis</i>	PI 673323 (OQK)	Diploid	7
<i>Helianthus porteri</i>	PI 673332 (HR)	Diploid	6
<i>Helianthus praecox</i> subsp. <i>praecox</i>	PI 435847 (TX)	Diploid	4
<i>Helianthus radula</i>	PI 673218 (RLR)	Diploid	2
<i>Helianthus resinusus</i>	PI 664695 (GA)	Hexaploid	5
<i>Helianthus salicifolius</i>	PI 664768 (PAO)	Diploid	1
<i>Helianthus silphioides</i>	PI 664795 (PAR)	Diploid	7
<i>Helianthus smithii</i>	PI 650087 (AL)	Tetraploid	10
<i>Helianthus winteri</i>	PI 673300 (CA)	Diploid	5
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Hornet (F1) – NuSeed	Diploid	5
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Hopi (Landrace) – Southern Exposure	Diploid	4
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Seneca (Landrace) – Southern Exposure	Diploid	5
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Mammoth (OPV) – Southern Exposure	Diploid	4
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Peredovik (OPV) – Southern Exposure	Diploid	5
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	EVE (Wild) – Everwilde Farms	Diploid	5
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	GBS (Wild) – Great Basin Seed	Diploid	4

Table S2. Accessions of wild *Helianthus* sorted by total number of compounds detected in floral volatiles, with counts of monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and other compounds identified in each. Samples from the parallel experiment across an *H. annuus* domestication gradient are listed at the end of the table.

Accession	Total Compounds	Monoterpenoids	Sesquiterpenoids	Other
<i>H. salicifolius</i>	9	7	2	0
<i>H. divaricatus</i> 2N	10	8	1	1
<i>H. maximiliani</i>	12	8	3	1
<i>H. heterophyllus</i>	19	7	2	10
<i>H. hirsutus</i>	22	9	12	1
<i>H. decapetalus</i> 4N	24	8	14	2
<i>H. resinosus</i>	25	12	11	2
<i>H. grosseserratus</i>	25	18	5	2
<i>H. laevigatus</i>	26	15	10	1
<i>H. carnosus</i>	26	13	11	2
<i>H. winteri</i>	28	13	11	4
<i>H. radula</i>	35	14	17	4
<i>H. floridanus</i>	35	17	17	1
<i>H. praecox</i> subsp. <i>praecox</i>	40	16	22	2
<i>H. decapetalus</i> 2N	42	14	25	3
<i>H. longifolius</i>	48	17	28	3
<i>H. debilis</i> subsp. <i>tardiflorus</i>	49	22	24	3
<i>H. porteri</i>	50	21	28	1
<i>H. annuus</i>	57	22	26	9
<i>H. angustifolius</i>	58	20	32	6
<i>H. mollis</i>	59	20	38	1
<i>H. silphioides</i>	60	23	31	6
<i>H. occidentalis</i>	61	24	34	3
<i>H. smithii</i>	62	26	26	10
<i>H. giganteus</i>	66	30	25	11
<i>H. argophyllus</i>	77	29	42	6
<i>H. atrorubens</i>	86	35	44	7
Wild <i>H. annuus</i> (EVE)	25	15	9	1
Wild <i>H. annuus</i> (GBS)	28	18	8	2
Cultivated - Mammoth (OPV)	29	18	10	1
Cultivated – Hopi (Landrace)	38	19	18	1
Cultivated – Hornet (F1)	38	19	18	1
Cultivated – Seneca (Landrace)	44	20	20	4
Cultivated – Peredovik (OPV)	48	26	17	5

Table S3. Accession means for mass-normalized peak area for volatile organic compounds listed by chemical subclass. Accessions are sorted from lowest total abundance to highest total abundance. *H. annuus* accessions are listed at the end of the table and are sorted from lowest total abundance to highest total abundance.

Accession	Total Volatiles	Monoterpenoids	Sesquiterpenoids	Other
<i>H. decapetalus</i> 4N	2486370	1611628	642092	232650
<i>H. hirsutus</i>	2648217	1781600	627406	239211
<i>H. maximiliani</i>	3249107	3113743	72592	62772
<i>H. salicifolius</i>	5410136	5343918	66218	0
<i>H. grosseserratus</i>	6420173	6203729	102415	114029
<i>H. divaricatus</i> 2N	6746191	6616086	35721	94383
<i>H. resinusus</i>	10275171	9500428	409086	365657
<i>H. smithii</i>	13267864	9020080	1844783	2403000
<i>H. decapetalus</i> 2N	13508838	9399564	1676203	2433071
<i>H. giganteus</i>	15548325	13410895	1033468	1103962
<i>H. praecox</i> subsp. <i>praecox</i>	15813662	14444425	1177943	191295
<i>H. radula</i>	16031033	14752623	389396	889015
<i>H. carnosus</i>	17454815	17094936	267359	92519
<i>H. angustifolius</i>	18122731	15380018	1171855	1570859
<i>H. floridanus</i>	19186920	18271249	574897	340774
<i>H. porteri</i>	19191951	17344773	1486341	360838
<i>H. laevigatus</i>	26790963	26172568	445928	172467
<i>H. silphioides</i>	28594802	25640519	1276973	1677310
<i>H. atrorubens</i>	30734801	27139253	2223013	1372536
<i>H. mollis</i>	33202519	29688989	3327552	185977
<i>H. argophyllus</i>	36198349	34183792	1607615	406941
<i>H. winteri</i>	36504025	35330903	244672	928450
<i>H. annuus</i>	36535984	34197807	654221	1683956
<i>H. heterophyllus</i>	37060338	3679983	71511	33308844
<i>H. occidentalis</i>	40825406	38778761	1787843	258802
<i>H. longifolius</i>	46440808	42032037	3324497	1084274
<i>H. debilis</i> subsp. <i>tardiflorus</i>	87069515	84838994	1951522	278999
Cultivated – Seneca (Landrace)	12898741	12500613	274339	123789
Cultivated – Mammoth (OPV)	16458256	15700900	652376	104980
Cultivated – Hopi (Landrace)	19067469	18195800	743734	127935
Wild <i>H. annuus</i> (EVE)	23314419	22730642	371833	211943
Cultivated – Hornet (F1)	24414092	23527387	764991	121714
Wild <i>H. annuus</i> (GBS)	25416572	24911408	371942	133221
Cultivated – Peredovik (OPV)	34150061	32172447	643845	1333769

